

ISic3457

Dedication to Venus Equestris

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone (Trapani)

Object

tympanum

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Excavated 2 February 2005 in area immediately to east of the church of
S. Giovanni Battista on Capo Boeo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 49 cm
Width 108 cm
Depth 24 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 55 mm

Text

1. [L(ucius) Plinius L(uci) f(ilius) Ruf]us leg(atus) pro pr(aetore) pr
(aetor) desig(natus) Veneri Eque [stri don(um) ded(it)]

Apparatus

Text of Silvestrini 2014

Translation (en)

[Lucius Plinius Rufus, son of Lucius] propraetorian legate, praetor designate,
[gave this as a gift]
to Venus Equestris

Commentary

Silvestrini 2014 plausibly suggests that this is a dedication set up by L. Plinius L.f. Rufus, legatus pro praetore of Sextus Pompeius and praetor designate for 33 BC, already attested at Lilybaeum in ILLRP 426 = ISic 0007. The inscription is referenced within AE 2007.678-679, although neither lemma there concerns this text.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644934

Bibliography

Silvestrini, M. 2014. Nuove epigrafi da Lilibeo. In Zaccaria, C.(eds.), *L'Epigrafia dei porti. Atti della XVIIe recncontre sur l'épigraphie du monde romain, Aquileia, 14-16 ottobre 2010*. Trieste. pp. 207-226. At 211-215 no.2 fig.5-6

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